

SOCIAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF FORMING THE PSYCHOLOGY OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE AMONG YOUTH

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Abstract. *The article deals with the problems of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle in the family, its formation and possible social and psychological ways to solve these problems. Illuminated, scientific and practical results of research related to healthier lifestyle of the individual.*

Keywords: *healthy generation, healthy lifestyle, psychology of a healthy lifestyle, socio-psychological factors in the formation of a healthy lifestyle.*

In the years of independence, the main goal was to build a just democratic society in our country, and consistent steps were taken towards this goal. Important results were also achieved in the construction of the civil society, which is the fairest social space that fully takes into account human interests and rights, and realizes his age-old dreams. Further formation of a healthy lifestyle in society, strengthening of population health, education of a physically healthy and spiritually rich young generation, ensuring wide involvement of citizens in physical education and sports are among the priorities of the active reform policy implemented in our country.

When talking about a healthy lifestyle, we are used to imagine that it is first of all getting rid of harmful habits that cause the human body to become sick. This term is explained primarily in relation to the activities of health workers. However, in the formation of a healthy way of life - body and mind, mind and perception directly depend on a person, so psychology, which is a science that studies the laws and secrets of the human psyche, is related to it. That's why there is a concept of healthy lifestyle psychology in the science of psychology, which looks at a healthy lifestyle first of all as a reflection of the human mind and thinking. Therefore, ensuring our health, which is necessary for each of us, like water and air, and getting used to a healthy lifestyle in order to achieve this, appears as a research subject not only of medical workers, but also of psychologists and the science of psychology.

In this sense, when psychology studies from the point of view of human behavior, behavior and various psychological states in the formation of a healthy lifestyle: basically, what aspects of our psyche that seem to be a secret are related to the feeling of health, well-being and vitality of each of us, by managing it, we are our wealth. - what opportunities are available in our hands to maintain our health and the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle, as a science and a useful practice that studies how to manage our own mental state, keep it moderate by timely progressing the changes in our consciousness, adapt to changing conditions, prevention in this regard is increasingly boldly entering our lives [1].

According to the sources, the psychology of a healthy lifestyle is a life aimed at maintaining and strengthening health by organizing daily life based on certain laws, and how life is, depends on how to organize one's life.

Health, a person's attitude to his health, should be considered as an important component of a person. It can be said that this field was created thanks to the fact that the society began to realize that it is unable to solve health problems on its own. "Risk factors" are associated with morbidity and mortality, so their study and assessment are relevant to both psychology and medicine [2]. However, based on the results of many studies, it should be noted that today the representatives of the medical field cannot solve the health problem on their own without turning to pedagogues and psychologists. The health problems of the medical workers themselves are increasing year by year [3].

A number of socio-psychological problems are encountered in the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle among the population, and especially among young people. Below we will try to think about some such social-psychological problems in the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle.

First, it is true that the field of mental health, which is considered the basis of a healthy lifestyle, has become an area of major research in a short period of time. We should note that the following numbers prove this situation. If in 1975 there were 200 mental health care programs in the US, by 1990 such programs had increased to 5,000. Currently, they show significant economic efficiency. Currently, one in ten psychologists in the United States is dealing with one or another problem of mental health, and one in three articles published in English-language psychological journals is related to various aspects of this field [4].

His comprehensive practical expression different organizational decisions is being strengthened with the help of For example , Great In Britain, " Nation health " document acceptance done if so , in Europe the mental and physical health to improve directed such initiative " Health all for ”.

Health psychology field specialists not only general psychological preparedness, but also psychohygiene, psychoprophylaxis, as well as psychosomatic health and psychotherapy issues according to too deep knowledge have to be necessary.

Secondly, we often compare and contrast people living in the city and in the countryside, and put down some of the shortcomings in their way of life, saying, "Well, it's rural, there's no chance." But the way of life of a person has nothing to do with it, I think. No matter where or under what circumstances any person lives, he tries to make himself comfortable in the first place. Because this convenience determines his daily life, his lifestyle and health. Let's take a room created for our needs, which we simply leave in our daily life, enter and exit several times during the day. Some people have uncomfortable places where they go to the bathroom, where the wind blows from all sides, where it is not comfortable to sit, and we even see houses surrounded by rice paddies. Don't you say that it will be built from places that are difficult to go to in winter? Children walking on mud and snow cause them to get sick. So does it cost that much? Or is it a person's negligence, that is, not knowing what the consequences will be? When you see that such people have houses decorated with expensive furniture and equipment, spend money on extravagant weddings, you think that "they simply do not have the opportunity to make their toilet as in the brochure". Also, don't you tell me that there is no bathroom to wash in and out at least once a week? What if there is no hammam in the neighborhood or village? Even if all this is repeated again, it can be assessed as a lack of lifestyle culture and low spirituality in a person. As a result , we open the way to the origin of various diseases, especially for women, to become a disease spreading factor , and we openly show our lack of civilization. We are far from saying that all the

people who live in the village are in such a situation, the opportunities created in some households can be said to be better than those of the city dwellers.

Thirdly, the ability to live a healthy lifestyle does not appear suddenly in a person, as it requires specific skills, it should be taught in the family from early childhood. This is one of the most important and responsible tasks of parents. All parents, while raising their children, always strive to be alert and watchful. This attention may be limited to standards such as checking that the child has enough things, is healthy, and regularly attends classes. For example, we wake up from sleep, our mind is busy with today's plans and their implementation, big and small, pleasant and unpleasant, but today's necessary and cannot be postponed. Our most important "concern" is our child. Waking up, bathing, feeding, dressing and taking him to kindergarten or school on time, we remember him again during our daily chores, we think he has come from school, we call and emphasize that he should be a good boy and do his lessons. When we come back from work, we plunge into endless household chores, among which we check the child's lessons, whether we can spend a little time with him for a conversation or not... and the next day it repeats itself. We are so used to it that we hardly think about our actions, on the contrary, our brains are occupied with completely different thoughts during these actions. How did the child wake up? Did they help prepare breakfast, set the table? How did you go to school? How did they say goodbye? How did he respond to your last rebuke? How does he spend his time? Can it be distributed correctly? How is it being formed as a person in general? These and thousands of similar questions may seem to melt, but all these are the environment that creates the environment for the future member of the society to be formed as a person in the future.

According to our observations, it is necessary to find solutions to the following socio-psychological problems that serve to solve the problem of forming a healthy lifestyle psychology among young people:

- to reveal the social and psychological aspects of the formation of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle from a pedagogical and psychological point of view;
- to study the experiences of foreign countries on the development of the psychology of a healthy lifestyle and reveal the scope and content of its use in the education system of young people;
- socio-psychological aspects of the development of healthy lifestyle psychology among young people, theoretically based on determining its effectiveness in practical experiments;
- to determine the place and position in the educational process of the educational system of forming the psychology of a healthy lifestyle of young people and to develop an effective system;
- development of socio-psychological trainings aimed at developing the psychology of a healthy lifestyle of young people, evaluating their content and effectiveness.

Summarizing the above, it can be noted that the psychology of a healthy lifestyle, on the one hand, refers to the physical health and maturity of a person, and on the other hand, the spiritual, ideological and mental health of a person is the basis of his full maturity as a person.

Only a person who feels healthy not only physically, but also socially and mentally can be an active member of society and benefit himself and others. After all, if the family and the young generation are healthy - the society is strong, if the society is strong - the country is stable.

REFERENCES

1. Оила психологияси. Академик лицей ва касб-хунар коллежлари ўқувчилари учун дарслик. /Проф. Ф.Б.Шоумаров тахрири остида. - Тошкент, 2008.
2. Allen, I. (1988) *Doctors and their Careers*. London: Policy Studies Institute.
3. Bennet, G. (1987) *The Wound and the Doctor: Healing Technology and Power in Modern Medicine*. London: Seeker & Warburg.
4. Borril, C. S., Wall, M. A., West, G. E., et al (1996) *Mental Health of the Workforce in NHS Trusts*. Leeds: Institute of Work Psychology, University of Sheffield & Department of Psychology, University of Leeds.
5. Саидов А., Джураев Р. Баркамол авлодни тарбиялаш-соғлом турмуш тарзини шакллантиришда спортнинг ўрни //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 203-208.
6. Саидов А. pedagogic mahorat: ёшлар ўртасида соғлом турмуштарзини шакллантириш устувор вазифа сифатида //центр научных публикаций (buxdu. uz). – 2020. – Т. 2. – №. 2.
7. SharifjonTo'lqin o'g A. et al. TA'LIM-TARBIYA TIZIMI VA O'QITUVCHILAR FAOLIYATIDA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMATNING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 11. – С. 57-60.
8. Саидов А. СОҒЛОМ ВА БАРКАМОЛ ШАХСИ ТАРБИЯЛАШНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК МАСАЛАЛАРИ //Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS). – 2021. – Т. 1. – №. Specialissue. – С. 262-266.
9. Саидов А., Джураев Р. Воспитание гармоничного поколения–роль спорта в формировании здорового образа жизни //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 2. – С. 203-208.
10. Saidov A. Historical roots of formation of healthy lifestyle culture psychology in the family //International Journal of Pharmaceutical Research. – 2020. – Т. 12. – №. 4. – С. 628-630.
11. Ismailovich A. S. PROBLEMS OF IMPROVING PSYCHOLOGY OF HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF UZBEK FAMILY //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 313-318.
12. Ismoilovich S. A. SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF THE FORMATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGY OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE OF FAMILIES
13. Ibraimov Kh. I. Creativity as one of the characteristics of the personality of the future teacher // Science, education and culture. – 2018. – no. 3 (27). - P. 44-46.
14. Ibragimovich Kh.I. Peculiarities of using credit-module technologies in the higher education system of Uzbekistan //Integration of science, education and practice. Scientific-methodical journal. - 2021. - P. 209-214.
15. Ibraimov Kh. "Theoretical and methodological basis of quality control and evaluation of education in higher education system." International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education 1 (2020): 6-15.
16. Ibragimov, X., Abdullayeva Sh. "Pedagogika nazariyasi (darslik)." T.: Fan va texnologiya 288 (2008).
17. Ibraimov X.I., M.Quronov. Umumiy pedagogika (darslik). –Т., “Shaffof”, 2023, 416-bet.

18. Ibragimovich I. K. et al. PEDAGOGICAL ABILITIES OF A TEACHER, STRUCTURE AND DEVELOPMENT //湖南大学学报 (自然科学版). – 2021. – Т. 48. – №. 12.
19. Ибрагимов Х. И. ПЕДАГОГИКА И ВОСПИТАНИЕ //Экономика и социум. – 2021. – №. 1-1 (80). – С. 608-611.
20. Ibragimovich, Ibraimov Kholboy. "Intensive methods of teaching foreign languages at university." Вопросы науки и образования 27 (39) (2018): 78-80.
21. Ибраимов Х. И. Педагогические и психологические особенности обучения взрослых //Academy. – 2019. – №. 10 (49). – С. 39-41.
22. Ибрагимов Х. И. Организация самостоятельной работы студентов в условиях цифровизации вузовского образования //Наука и образование сегодня. – 2020. – №. 7 (54). – С. 74-75.
23. Ibragimov, X. I., U. A. Yo'ldoshev, and X. Bobomirzayev. "Pedagogik psixologiya." O'quv qo'llanma. O'zbekiston faylasuflari milliy jamiyati nashiriyoti Toshkent (2009).